

Burn skin Treatment and Platelet-rich plasma Therapy:

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Burns are tissue damage that outcomes from heat, overexposure to the sun or other radiation, or chemical or electric contact. Burns can be minor medical problems or life-threatening emergencies. {1} The treatment of burns depends at the area and severity of the harm. Sunburns and small scalds can typically be handled at home. Deep or good sized burns want on the spot clinical attention. {2} A few people need treatment at specialized burn facilities and months long and follow up care. Burn signs and symptoms relying on how deep the pores and skin damage is. It can take a day or two day for the signs and symptoms and signs of an intense burn to develop. First degree burns. This minor burn affects only the outer layer of skin (the epidermis). {3} It causes redness and pain. Second degree burns. This type of burn affects both the epidermis and the second layer of skin (dermis). It causes swelling and red, white, or blotchy skin. Blisters can form and the pain can be severe. Deep second-degree burns leave scars. Third degree burns. This burn can extend into the layer of fat under the skin. The burned area can be black, brown, or white. The skin may look like leather. {4}

Platelets are best known for their ability to clot blood, but they also contain growth factors that trigger cell multiplication and stimulate tissue regeneration or healing in the treated area {5}. Platelet-rich plasma is blood that contains more platelets than normal. We can use a PRP in order to treat a burn skin because PRP have trigger tissue regeneration. {6}

Method to Treat a Burn skin by using PRP Therapy:

Treatment is depending upon the following steps:

- **Plasma Preparation:**

It can be centrifuged, i.e., Whole blood containing anticoagulant is centrifuged in a centrifuge to separate it from the whole blood. Plasma is lighter in color, forming a yellowish layer at the top; while denser blood

cells fall to the bottom and plasma contain a growth factor and many other factors including platelets which is important for skin regeneration. {7}

- **PRP Therapy Injection:**

After conceiving platelet-rich from a patient blood the PRP solution is directly injected into the targeted area such as skin. {8} The mechanism at the back of PRP injections is Studies display that the increased attention of growth factors in platelet rich plasma might also stimulate or speed up the healing system. {9}

Burn skin Case study and Treatment:

A 24 year female is present to the emergency room with 2rd degree burn in the leg with drain pus and severs pain. Before skin grafting we can try a PRP in order to regenerated tissues of the skin. We can direct inject a PRP into the burn area and after 1-week we can see that PRP stimulate the skin healing system.

Before PRP Therapy

After PRP Therpay skin is healing

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